

PEDAGOGICAL MANAGEMENT AND ADMINISTRATION IN A MODERN SCHOOL

Abstract:

The article examines the essence of pedagogical management and administrative activities at school. The purpose of the article is to reveal the possibilities and aspects of the implementation of management activities in an educational institution. The authors of the article analyzed a study on the essence and definition of pedagogical management in

Key words:

pedagogical management, administrative activities, school, resources, teaching staff, goals, educational organization.

Author of the article:

Do`sjonova Nilufar Rustam qizi

Workspace (Education subject)

3 years students, Undergraduate degree Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Azhiniyaz

Introduction. In the context of changes in legislation in the field of education and the emergence of innovative structures, approaches to understanding and assessing the quality of school education are changing somewhat. It is possible to ensure quality in education with the help of a well-functioning management system that contributes to the satisfaction of internal and external consumers: students and their parents, employers, employees and the state.

Management of an educational organization is a specific activity for organizing, monitoring, maintaining, planning and ensuring organized joint educational and educational activities of students, pedagogical activities and activities of another educational institution. It is aimed at fulfilling the tasks assigned to them to fulfill the comprehensive mission of the school, obtaining quality education, teaching and developing educational organizations.

Presentation of the main material of the article. Various aspects of management, in particular psychological and pedagogical, based on the activity approach in education, are considered in the scientific works of such domestic authors as: S.L. Rubinstein, A.G. Asmolov, A.N. Leontiev, L.S. Vygotsky and others.

In the scientific works of T.I. Shamova, Yu.V. Vasilyeva, P.I. Tretyakova, T.M. Davydenko, M.M. Potashnikova, Yu.A. Konarzhevsky considered the basics of training specialists in the field of management and the formation of their skills and abilities in management activities.

The parameters of a specialist's readiness to carry out managerial activities in educational organizations, as well as methodological and practical recommendations on the formation and conduct of management activities in the school.

According to V.Yu. Krichevsky, management is a subject-subjective relationship, that is, the impact of the subject of pedagogical management on it, the interaction of various pedagogical subsystems of control and control, the formation between leadership and subordination on the basis of interaction and coordination of common goals, tasks, methods, means and actions. I.F. Isaev carries out pedagogical management activities such as the use of decisions, control, supervision and regulation of the control object, based on the set goals and the collection of information, analysis and summing up. P.I. Tretyakov believes that management is a certain oriented activity of the subjects of the management group at various levels to ensure the high-quality functioning and optimal work of the managed group,

The concept of "management", in turn, the researchers associate with the creative activity of the subject of management to achieve the assigned tasks of education and training. V.P. Simonov the concept of "pedagogical management", as a specific set of management systems, attitudes, methods and means of managing pedagogical systems, concentrated and used to improve the quality and efficiency of educational systems management.

V.A. Sitarov interprets pedagogical management as "a new social phenomenon as the organization of upbringing, development, training and the formation of the managerial competence of government representatives in the system of state and municipal government".

"The originality of the pedagogical sphere is due to the character and nature of educational activity. Training and education creates a kind of product that is not similar to the products of other industries and fields of activity. The product of the school is a person, because "pedagogical production" has different characteristics, management in pedagogical systems has a certain specificity". These functions may include the following: a strong dependence of the educational organization on consumers, the impossibility of creating resources, the need to search for personnel of training methods, the cyclical installation of individual educational services, the difficulty of determining the effectiveness of work.

Management in the field of education or pedagogical management is a set of actions taken within the framework of the management of an educational institution. It is customary to consider pedagogical management in the unity of such components as:

- resource management of an educational organization. It is involved in the planning, accounting and distribution of material and financial resources of the school to ensure the optimal functioning of the educational organization. This activity is carried out in conjunction and interaction with the management of the teaching staff and education at school and is one of the main activities in the management of the educational system;
- management of the educational process at school. This activity is carried out with the aim of achieving didactic educational, educational, educational goals, the development of each student through the educational, educational process and other educational, carried out educational organization in accordance with the state educational standard:

- management of the teaching staff of the educational.

Collective consumption of resources in the educational process.

V.A. Sitarov identifies the following components of pedagogical management: educational, motivational, cognitive, activity, creative, informational, integrative. Other authors use that its components are the formation of motivation, the choice of certain goals (goals) for managing the process at school, the establishment of subject-subject relations, control over the formation of knowledge, skills and abilities of students.

Based on the listed components, pedagogical management reveals its essence as:

I can't find what you are looking for? Service try the selection of literature.

- a set of techniques, methods, technologies and tools for managing the educational process and the pedagogical and student body of the system, that is, the implementation of integrated management of the overall process of implementation of the educational organization and educational activities of educational activities carried out by active subjects of management of the pedagogical process, namely the school director, his deputies, teachers;
- a set of necessary competencies of a leader in managing an educational organization, his ability to use his own labor, intellect, pedagogical and managerial experience for the set educational goals of an educational organization, which act as the interaction and unification of two arts, people management and management of various processes at school.

In the structure of pedagogical management, the following levels are conditionally level.

The pedagogical process is characterized by the systemic nature of management, both vertically and horizontally. Considering the vertical, the levels of the following levels of management:

- the level of public management;
- the level of regional management;
- regional level of management;
- the level of management of educational institutions;
- the level of management of departments of educational institutions.

The horizontal level of the level is the following: professional qualities of the teacher, training sessions, independent extracurricular work, etc.

In addition, at the school level, you can also use such a level as the management of pedagogical projects, since they are independent areas. The projects can be training sessions using active forms of education, educational and recreational activities, etc.

Management activity in educational activities depends on the methods, goals, objectives and conditions of the pedagogical situation of the teacher who implements it [5]. Many researchers believe that management activities at school can be optimized and effective when the following conditions and principles are achieved that underlie the professional and pedagogical management activities:

- moral and financial encouragement of pedagogical initiative;
- recognition for the object of management of his personal qualities, the importance of the rights to freedom, creativity and expression of position on the issue under consideration within the framework of the educational organization;
- decisions are made on the basis of universal agreement and approval, the creation of a team with common principles and ideas;
- development of the teaching and student collective as one of the main areas of activity of the educational organization;
- control directed from bottom to top;
- flexibility in management, the possibility of transition, from centralized management of educational activities to decentralized in the case of the prevailing circumstances or the type of problem situations in the educational organization.

So the goals of management activities at different levels are different. Work at the first level is carried out with the help of the effective pedagogical activity of the school teacher through the implementation of creative pedagogical lessons. At the level of achieving the goals of productive and effective management of the educational process, the formation of personal qualities in students, through the implementation of the abilities of their creative potential.

The head of the educational organization plays a leading role and the success of the school depends on what style of work he chooses. Thus, the headmaster must have leadership qualities. The following leaderships of the educational organization stand out.

The leader who uses the elements of technical leadership in his work is quite successful, competently organizes and coordinates the educational process, has certain knowledge in drawing up the school budget.

A leader who uses elements of human leadership pays special attention to the formation of moral values among teachers and students.

A leader who uses elements of educational leadership, first of all, pays his attention to the problems of the school and teachers.

The leader, which is a type of symbolic leadership, is the symbol of the school. Very often people do not know the school by the name or number of the school, but by the name of the principal. Such a director is interested in how the teachers conduct classes and make rounds of the school.

Chief, using elements of cultural leadership, maintains their traditions and new school staff. Educators themselves are educational organizations with a strong culture.

Conclusions. Thus, in the educational organization, but there is a different interpretation from different authors. This fact is associated with the creation of the educational sphere, the emergence of new functions for the management of educational programs, etc. That and indicate the relevance and necessity of researching the essence and process of pedagogical management and management activities in an educational organization.

References

1. Bystrova N.V., Zinovieva S.A., Filatova E.V. Principles of the modern educational process // Problems of modern pedagogical education. - 2020. - No. 67-4. - S. 68-70.

I can't find what you are looking for? Service try the selection of literature.

2. Bystrova N.V., Kaznacheeva S.N., Urakova E.A., Goselbakh O.I. Features of psychological well-being of students in the educational environment // Innovative economy: prospects for development and improvement. - 2019. - No. 5 (39). - S. 26-31.

3. Bystrova N.V., Tsyplakova S.A. Information and educational environment of the school as an innovative management task // Science and Practice of Regions. - 2019. - No. 4 (17). - S. 90-93.
4. Grigoryan N.M., Bystrova N.V. Personal development of a teacher in the vocational education system // In the collection: Social and technical services: problems and ways of development. Collection of articles based on the materials of the V All-Russian scientific-practical conference. Nizhny Novgorod State Pedagogical University named after K. Minin. - 2018. -- S. 35-38.
5. Markova S.M., Kotenko E.F., Urakova E.A. Designing management of the educational process by the integration process // In the collection: Innovative approaches to solving professional and pedagogical problems. Collection of articles based on the materials of the All-Russian scientific-practical conference. Minin University. - 2019. -- S. 37-39.
6. Markova S.M., Tsyplakova S.A. Management of the pedagogical process as a system // School of the Future. - 2016. - No. 4. - S. 138-144.
7. Sitarov V.A. Pedagogical management as theory and practice of educational process management // Knowledge. Understanding. Skill. - 2014. - No. 3. URL: <https://cyberienmka.ru/artide/n/pedagogicheskij-menedzhment-kak-teoriya-i-praktika-upravleniya-obrazovatelnyim-protsessom> (date of access: 16.05.2021).